
Psychological Interpretation of Creativity Development in Primary Class Students

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***Annotation.** In this article, scientific and psychological comments about the important factors, conditions, manifestations and the educational attitude towards the creativity of elementary school students are highlighted.*

***Keywords:** Characteristics of creativity, level of creativity, logical thinking, creative thinking, imaginative creativity, creative approach, ability, ideational orientation, fluency, intelligence, cognitive, differential.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the development of creativity in students from the elementary school age has become an urgent issue of youth periods and modern educational psychology. Early detection and formation of this ability, its importance in the general formation and maturity of the student, scientifically substantiates the dependence of the individual's success on the level of creativity in the future. In order to logically systematize such studies and to form the characteristics of creativity in students, we aimed to comprehensively study the characteristics of creativity in students.

Oriental thinkers have a great place in the views on the development of creative features in the personality of a child. Eastern thinkers have important opinions and opinions about the need to use various methods and tools of education and create the necessary conditions in the process of education and formation of a creative and creative thinker, a well-rounded person.

The great thinker Yusuf Khos Hajib in his work "Kutadgu bilig" - (Knowledge that leads to happiness) explains that logical, creative and positive thinking of a person is based on perfection. In the example, the work shows knowledge, creativity and noble (positive) thinking as the main aspects of a perfect person. He suggests that a perfect person can fully understand reality through these qualities and can think

beautifully and creatively through this intelligence. He claims that his knowledge is great - his education is great. Because an intelligent person will be great, and a learned person will be great, so he adds learned people to the original category of people. The scientist claims that all good deeds are done because of science.

The idea that a person can acquire healthy behavior and high spirituality through beautiful and creative thinking is also widely covered in Kaikovus's work "Nightmare". He divides science into three parts: 1. Science that depends on a profession. 2. Profession related to science. 3. A custom related to blessings and signs.

These views of Kaikovus were among the progressive views of that time. Because these thoughts showed that he was intelligent, wise, and had comprehensive knowledge. In his advices about mental, moral and physical education of every young person, the work "Nightmare" is of great practical importance in raising a mature generation.

The encyclopedist Abu Raikhan Beruni in his works explains which aspects should be paid more attention to in order to develop the student's creative and independent thinking. In particular, we can see that the scientist stated that it is important not to memorize, but to follow the path of understanding, logical and creative thinking, drawing conclusions [3; 103-b].

According to Abu Rayhan Beruni, a person has the ability to know, understand, think, discuss, and invent. The power of a person's creative and logical thinking is that by comparing events and phenomena with each other, by analyzing them, it is possible to distinguish truth from lies, justice from injustice, good from evil, and truth from injustice. "A person is in control of his passions, he is able to change them, while training his soul and body, he is able to turn negative aspects into praiseworthy things and gradually eliminate vices by the methods shown in the books on ethics." emphasizes.

According to Abu Rayhan Beruni, a person compares things and events on the basis of his creative and logical thinking, intellect, and realizes the truth of his thoughts, that is, he compares knowledge with objective reality. Thus, the great scientist puts forward the methods of creative and logical activity such as analysis, comparison, and these methods are interpreted as thinking operations in modern psychology. The great scientist Abu Nasr Farabi tried to determine the specific characteristics of acquiring knowledge through reason and logical thinking. In his works, it is explained that creative thinking has existence, generality, that is, knowing through intuition. According to Farabi's teachings, on the basis of thinking, a person understands aspects of existence unknown to the senses, his own laws, acquires information in the field of science and culture, and promotes the manifestation of creative thinking. According to him, one

of the most important tasks of the mind is to perform logical and creative operations. This activity is carried out with the help of creative thinking, concepts and judgments in thinking, and then ends with drawing conclusions.

In Alloma's teaching, there are also ideas about the direction of thinking from concreteness to abstraction and returning from abstraction to concreteness. In his treatise "On the Mind", Farobi says that only a person who combines 12 qualities will be a moral person. "The fifth of them is to be able to express his thoughts and opinions fluently so that his words are clear." It is these thoughts that show that our great ancestors emphasized that the independent and creative thinking of a person is his important quality [2; 224-b].

Abu Ali Ibn Sina, in his stories such as "Tair" (bird), "Hayy ibn Yaqzan", "Tadbiri Manzil" encourages people to learn scientifically, logically and creatively in order to deeply understand the essence of existence. Ibn Sina says about this: "The benefit of the science of wisdom is from the knowledge of cash. If you learn this science, it will show you the hidden nature of people. If you enjoy clairvoyance, you will become very sharp." Writing about the development of logical thinking, which is considered one of the main criteria of creative thinking, the scholar says, "If one acquires the science of logic, one's life will not sink in the environment." At this point, it can be noted that the educational views of Abu Ali Ibn Sina are based on the principles of high humanity and great humanitarian ideas [1; 315].

Also, the practical and scientific approaches to the formation of the child's independent thinking from a young age, and the formation of his all-round creative qualities, together with our great thinkers Muhammad Khorezmi, Abu Bakr Razi, Umar Khayyam, Mirza Ulugbek, Mir Alisher Navoi, the sultan of poetry. we can also see in the works of Imam Bukhari, Imam al-Tirmizi, Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband, Khoja Ahmed Yassavi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, who combined religious worldview and communal knowledge.

According to the general conclusions of many studies conducted in this direction, creativity is a necessary ability that allows a person to approach any change creatively and productively. The value of creativity means finding a way out of problematic situations in which old experience cannot be relied on or the necessary completeness of knowledge is not available. Solving a problem requires innovation - this is the essence of the creative process. So, it is clear from this definition that creativity is definitely creating something new, an unusual approach to solving a problem, avoiding the old.

In the studies of researchers I.Kant, I.Fixte, F.Schelling, G.Hegel, we can observe the movement to understand creativity. In particular, it can be observed that researchers came to the conclusion that

creativity is the foundation of a person's theoretical attitude to reality, his developed creative imagination [6; 179].

Our further research studies show that creativity is a combination of personal qualities, more than an adaptive feature, the importance of creativity is an opportunity to discover the abilities to show oneself to the world, to show one's own identity, which is one's own zi means to know.

In our observations on the formation of creativity characteristics in students of junior school age, it became clear that the main focus in the organization of the educational process is not on the development of effective thinking and imagination processes of students, but on the memory processes of information. , focuses on processes such as memorization, memorization, and recall. Unfortunately, creativity in general secondary schools, which traditionally exists in our country, does not include special measures aimed at consistently and systematically identifying and developing effective imagination in children, and as a result, the development of creativity by adults Not only the evaluation of the final product is observed. The reason for this is that teachers often do not know the basics of the psychology of creativity, the specific features of its formation, development, and manifestation. This problem becomes the most urgent problem for junior school age, because this period is characterized by sensitivity, the acquisition of the first organized experience of knowledge acquisition, the formation of self-representation and external evaluation.

Therefore, from the analysis of the results of many studies, it is clear that in order to take into account the mechanisms of formation of creative thinking in students of junior school age and to create conditions for the development of creativity, it is necessary to know the following factors and always calculate with these factors. These psychological factors are the following. Including

- conditions for the formation of creativity;
- forms of manifestation of creativity;
- interrelationship of basic new knowledge at junior school age with creativity in general and verbal and imaginative creativity in particular;
- the connection of creativity with cognitive and personal characteristics;
- the relationship between the level of creativity formed and the results of activity, in this case, the relationship with success in studying.

Researchers such as T. M. Amabil, F. Barron, J. W. McKinnon, R. Ochse, R. J. Sternberg and T. I. Lubart scientifically substantiated the fact that creativity is the ability to create innovation by creative approach to activity. The study of creativity is important not only for the above reasons, but also for the development

of this phenomenon as an experimental field of psychology. Indeed, every branch of psychology (cognitive, social, differential, youth, medical psychology) has contributed to the understanding of this research topic.

However, in our opinion, today it is necessary to combine these approaches. Creativity is a complex phenomenon. Psychological research examines how different approaches complement each other and how they can be combined methodologically.

P. Torrens identifies four characteristics of creativity (fluency, flexibility, originality, depth), V. Lowenfeld developed eight of them (ability to see the problem, fluency, flexibility, originality, synthesis and analysis ability, a sense of appropriateness in the organization of ideas).

In addition, P. Torrens claims that creative thinking enhances a person's ability to perceive flaws, defects, missing elements, knowledge gaps and inconsistencies [4; 42].

The concept of creativity as a phenomenon of creativity was first introduced to science by the American psychologist J. Gilford, who conducted extensive research. At the end of the 50s of the last century, he formulated several criteria that can be evaluated in psychological tests for creativity [4; 267].

Main criteria:

1. Fluency of thought - the number of ideas that arise in a certain time unit, the humor that creates ideas.
2. Flexibility of thought - the ability to switch from one thought to another.
3. Uniqueness - the ability to develop thoughts that differ from stereotypes, the ability to respond to stimuli in a non-standard way.
4. Curiosity - sensitivity to problems, surrounding situations, receptivity - sensitivity to unusual details, contradictions and uncertainties, readiness to quickly switch from one idea to another.
5. The ability to develop a hypothesis - an independent opinion, which should be carefully checked later.
6. Satisfaction is the result of creativity - the logical independence of reactions from stimuli, the ability to solve problems, analyze and synthesize.

Psychologist A. Maslow described creativity as an innate characteristic that everyone has, but it fades under the influence of the social environment [7; 425].

In the process of globalization, there is a need to use non-traditional types of creative thinking to solve problems.

Creativity occurs in the process of developing images and ideas, on the basis of a person confirming his point of view and mastering the experience of ancestors. It covers the assimilation of information, observation of reality, logical integration of knowledge and creativity.

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Creativity features begin to form in the early childhood. One of the main directions of the science of developmental psychology and pedagogical psychology is the research of the manifestation, formation and development of creativity in childhood. Children's creativity is especially evident in their play activities. Imitative features prevail in children's play activities. On the basis of imitation, they enrich and improve the behavior of adults.

Creativity is a person's ability to come up with new ideas and develop unusual ideas. In psychology, creativity is studied as an activity aimed at finding solutions to problems. In the educational process, intellectual activity is formed on the basis of practical, objective activity. It is appropriate to pay special attention to the sources of creative thinking, its formation and development.

Based on the above theoretical analysis of the research conducted on the category of creativity, we came to the conclusion that creativity is a very complex and comprehensive process. Representatives of each direction not only interpret the concept of "creativity" in their own way, but also use different methods of diagnosing creativity.

In fact, all the considerations show that it is possible to form it only by studying the laws of formation of creativity characteristics of students of junior school age, the specific characteristics of the category of creativity, which are important psychological factors.

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